

Direct observation of electronic conductivity transitions and solid electrolyte interphase stability of Na₂Ti₃O₇ electrodes for Na-ion batteries

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Highlights

- First experimental evidence of conductivity change upon Na⁺ insertion in Na₂Ti₃O₇.
- EIS shows instability of the SEI layer which contributes to the capacity fading.
- SEI dissolution and conductivity change are reversible upon cycling.
- Increase of surface roughness and heterogeneity during cycling as determined by EIS.

Abstract

This communication reports the first experimental evidence of an interesting change of transport properties, and particularly of electron conductivity, during the Na⁺ insertion/extraction process in Na₂Ti₃O₇ negative electrodes. Probed by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy, for $0.0 \leq x < 1.4$ in Na_{2+x}Ti₃O₇ the material exhibits insulator behaviour, the bulk electronic conductivity being the limiting factor in the insertion process. After further Na⁺ insertion, the material becomes electronic conductor and at around 0.13 V vs. Na⁺/Na the rate of interfacial charge-transfer becomes the limiting factor. The observed conductivity transition is reversible upon cycling. Additionally, this impedance study sheds new light on the solid electrolyte interphase layer performance which is found to be unstable upon electrochemical cycling and negatively contributes on the capacity fading observed for this electrode material.

1. Introduction

Na₂Ti₃O₇ is a promising negative electrode for rechargeable Na-ion batteries (NIBs) since it has a very low insertion voltage (0.3 V vs. Na⁺/Na) and high specific capacity (178 mA h/g) [1,2]. However, Na₂Ti₃O₇ shows poor capacity retention when synthesized from Na₂CO₃ as sodium precursor, reaching only 50-70% of capacity retention after 10 cycles [3-5]. The capacity fading is correlated, among other factors, with the presence of traces of Na₂CO₃ [3], which are originated by the interaction of Na₂Ti₃O₇ particles with atmospheric H₂O and CO₂. Another important concern to take into account in this

42 material is the formation of a stable solid electrolyte interphase (SEI) layer. In fact, the
43 reversible Na⁺ insertion/extraction reaction occurs at low potential and, therefore,
44 electrolyte reduction occurs. The stability and composition of this SEI layer has been
45 previously studied by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) [6], concluding that the
46 SEI layer formed upon Na⁺ insertion is partially dissolved during extraction. Therefore it
47 becomes necessary to better understand the SEI layer behaviour in order to find a good
48 combination of anode and electrolyte to form a stable SEI layer reaching a good
49 electrochemical performance.

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51 In order to gain new insights on the reasons behind the poor capacity retention of
52 Na₂Ti₃O₇, an electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) study was carried out to
53 determine the electronic and ionic transport properties of Na₂Ti₃O₇ electrodes.

54

55 2. Experimental

56 Na₂Ti₃O₇ was synthesized via a ceramic route using TiO₂ anatase (99.9%, Alfa Aesar) and
57 Na₂CO₃ · H₂O (>99.5%, Sigma Aldrich) in a 5% excess as Na precursor to avoid the
58 formation of Na₂Ti₆O₁₃ as secondary phase. The mixture was then heated in air up to
59 800 °C for 12 h twice [3]. The structural characterisation of Na₂Ti₃O₇ was done by powder
60 X-ray diffraction (PXRD) using a Bruker Advance D8 instrument with Cu radiation (Cu
61 Ka_{1,2} I = 1.5406 Å, 1.5444 Å). The PXRD pattern is shown in Fig. S1 of the Supplementary
62 Information and it corresponds to a pure single phase of Na₂Ti₃O₇. Moreover, the refined
63 cell parameters (Table S1 of the Supplementary Information) are in agreement with the
64 values published in the literature [7]. Electrodes were prepared by mixing 70% active
65 material, 20% carbon Super C65 (Timcal) and 10% polyvinylidene difluoride (PVdF,
66 Solef®5130) in N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP, Sigma Aldrich). The slurry was casted on
67 battery grade Al foil and dried under vacuum overnight at 120 °C. 9 mm electrode disks
68 with the active material load of 0.94 mg/cm² were punched and pressed at 5 tons before
69 cell assembling in an Ar-filled glove box. Three electrode Swagelok type cells were built
70 using metallic Na disks as counter and reference electrodes, glass fibre (Whatman GF B
71 55) as separator and 1 M NaClO₄ in EC:PC (ethylene carbonate: propylene carbonate,
72 1:1) as electrolyte. All electrochemical measurements were performed at room
73 temperature in the voltage window 0.05-1.6 V vs. Na⁺/Na using a VMP3 potentiostat
74 (Bio-Logic). Cyclic voltammetry (CV) was carried out in a half cell at 0.40 mV/s scan rate.
75 The galvanostatic data were collected at 0.1C rate. EIS measurements were performed
76 by controlling the electrode potential through PITT (potentiostatic intermittent titration
77 technique) intercalation and deintercalation scans with steps of 25 mV. Sinusoidal
78 perturbations of 5 mV, in the frequency range 5 mHz-100 kHz, were superimposed to
79 the bias potentials. In order to reach an equilibrium condition, 4 h equilibration time at
80 constant potential was allowed before recording each impedance spectra. Boukamp's
81 Equivalent Circuit software was used to fit all EIS data [8].

82

83 3. Results and discussion

84 The electrochemical response of Na₂Ti₃O₇ is presented in Fig. 1, where the CV curve of
85 the first and second cycles in the voltage window of 0.05-1.6 V vs. Na⁺/Na is shown (Fig.
86 1a). In the first cycle, two main reduction peaks at 0.32 V and 0.05 V and a shoulder

87 between 0.5 and 0.9 V vs. Na⁺/Na can be observed, along with one reversible oxidation
 88 peak at 0.34 V. The peak at 0.05 V corresponds to the insertion of Na⁺ into Na₂Ti₃O₇ [4]
 89 while the large shoulder in the potential range 0.9 > Ewe > 0.5 and the reduction peak
 90 at 0.32 V correspond to the decomposition reaction of the electrolyte during SEI layer
 91 formation which starts around 0.9 V [6]. The processes related to SEI formation are
 92 mostly irreversible, as confirmed by the CV curve in the voltage range 0.2-1.0 V (a broad
 93 shoulder can be observed in the inset of Fig. 1a). Nevertheless, in the following cycles
 94 upon Na⁺ insertion and extraction a broad hump appears which suggests the instability
 95 of the surface layers in contact with the liquid electrolyte as well as partial reversibility
 96 of the related processes. This is in agreement with the galvanostatic profile of Fig. 1b;
 97 every cycle is affected by some irreversible capacity which leads to a global capacity
 98 fading of the electrode. In other words, reduction of the electrolyte keeps taking place
 99 upon cycling.

100

101

102 Fig. 1. a) CV curve of the first (black) and second (red) cycles of Na₂Ti₃O₇ electrode at
 103 0.40 mV/s scan rate. The EIS measurements are performed in the highlighted points of
 104 the curve. Inset shows a zoom of the CV curves between 0.2 and 1.0 V vs. Na⁺/Na. b)
 105 Voltage vs. capacity of the first ten cycles at 0.1C. The capacity evolution during the first
 106 ten cycles is shown in the inset. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this
 107 figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

108 The Nyquist plots corresponding to the most relevant potential values during the 1st Na⁺
 109 insertion process are shown in Fig. 2. The impedance dispersion recorded at 1.0 V vs.
 110 Na⁺/Na (Fig. 2a) reveals a huge arc in the lowest-frequency region as the main feature
 111 and two more semicircles at higher frequencies. A similar feature has already been
 112 observed for Li⁺ intercalation electrodes that show an insulating behaviour, at least at
 113 certain intercalation degrees [9-11], and has been attributed to the bulk electron
 114 conductivity of the active material. When the dispersion is enlarged (Fig. 2b) further
 115 elements are revealed, namely a semicircle in the medium frequency region,
 116 overlapping with a smaller semicircle at the highest-frequency limit. The medium- and
 117 high-frequency semicircles are commonly assigned to charge-transfer/accumulation of
 118 charge at interfacial double layer and migration through solid electrolyte interphase
 119 layer, respectively. When the potential is lowered to the range 0.9-0.52 V (Fig. 2a), the
 120 huge arc starts progressively to contract and to bend onto the real axis. As the potential
 121 is further lowered and the amount of inserted Na⁺ increased (Fig. 2c), the diameter of
 122 the arc is reduced of about one order of magnitude. Below 0.4 V (Fig. 2c) the contraction
 123 of the low frequency semicircle is completed. A sloping line typical of a diffusive

124 behaviour is now revealed below 1 Hz, followed by a vertical line in the lowest-frequency
 125 region which describes accumulation of charge (differential intercalation capacity). At
 126 the same time, as shown in Fig. 2b and d, the medium-to-high frequency (above 50 Hz)
 127 features remain practically unmodified.

128

129 It is worth noting that the constant contraction of the lowest frequency semicircle as
 130 Na^+ content increases in the $\text{Na}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ electrode is the peculiar trend of the subsequently
 131 acquired impedance dispersion. A similar behaviour has been experimentally observed
 132 by EIS in $\text{LiCo}_x\text{Ni}_{1-x}\text{O}_2$ cathodes (in this case during Li^+ extraction) and it has been
 133 attributed to the change in the electronic conductivity which reveals a transition from
 134 insulator to conductor [9-11]. A similar behaviour has been also modelled by Barsoukov
 135 et al. [12,13], who assigned the trend of the low frequency arc to the EIS response of the
 136 change in crystalline structure of the LiCoO_2 material. On the light of these previous
 137 results, it can be inferred that $\text{Na}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ electrodes also follow an electronic conductivity
 138 change during Na^+ insertion: after complete oxidation ($E = 1.0 \text{ V}$, $\text{Na}_{2+x}\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$, $x < 0.0$) the
 139 active material behaves as an insulator showing a large semicircle at low frequency (Fig.
 140 2a) but, when it is completely reduced ($E = 0.05 \text{ V}$, $\text{Na}_{2+x}\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$, $x < 2.0$) it becomes an
 141 electronic conductor and the low-frequency semicircle decreases bending to the real
 142 axis (Fig. 2c). Recent first-principles calculations have ascribed the transition from
 143 insulator to electronic conductor to an excess of ionized electrons from inserted Na^+
 144 occupying the t_{2g} orbitals of Ti 3d in the $\text{Na}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ conduction band [4]. This transition has
 145 never been seen before in any electrode material for NIBs and the work reported here is the
 146 first experimental evidence of such behaviour. Furthermore, during the first Na^+
 147 extraction process the $\text{Na}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ exhibits the opposite behaviour (Fig. S2). The radius of
 148 the lowest frequency semicircle increases as Na^+ content is extracting in the $\text{Na}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$
 149 electrode, suggesting that the transition from insulator to metallic is reversible.

150

151

152 Fig. 2. Nyquist plot of $\text{Na}_{2+x}\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ electrode at the potential upon 1st Na^+ insertion of a) 1.0 V (x
153 = 0.0), 0.88 V ($x = 0.0$), 0.70 V ($x = 0.0$), 0.68 V ($x = 0.0$), 0.65 V ($x = 0.0$), 0.63 V ($x = 0.0$),
154 0.60 V ($x = 0.0$), b) Zoom of a) impedance data in the frequency region of 100 kHz-7 Hz c) 0.48
155 V ($x = 0.0$), 0.45 V ($x = 0.0$), 0.40 V ($x = 0.0$), 0.35 V ($x = 0.0$), 0.30 V ($x = 0.0$), 0.18 V ($x =$
156 0.70) and 0.05 V ($x = 2.0$) vs. Na^+/Na . d) Zoom of c) impedance data in the frequency range
157 of 100 kHz to 7 Hz.

158 In order to confirm the insulator to conductor transition and their reversibility, all the
159 impedance dispersion data have been fitted to an equivalent circuit (inset Fig. 4)
160 previously used for intercalation cathodes in LIBs [9-11]: the high-frequency intercept
161 onto the real axis is described by R_{sol} and corresponds to the Na^+ resistance across the
162 electrolyte; the high-frequency semicircle is described by a resistance and a capacitance
163 of the SEI layer (R_{SEI} and C_{SEI}) connected in parallel; the medium-frequency semicircle is
164 described the charge-transfer resistance (R_{CT}) and double layer capacitance (C_{DL}) in
165 parallel; the low-frequency semicircle is described by two components in parallel,
166 namely the electronic resistance (R_{elec}) and the capacitance coming from the
167 accumulation of charge at the surface of the particles or at intraparticles crystallite
168 domains (C_{elec}). Finally, the sloping line in the lowest frequency region can be described
169 as a series of a Warburg diffusion element (Z_{w}) [13] and an intercalation capacity (C_i)
170 [14], related to the solid-state diffusion of the Na^+ inside the crystal.

171

172 During the fitting procedures, all ZW and C elements have been substituted by constant
173 phase elements (CPEs) in order to take into account any inhomogeneity, roughness or
174 other deviation from ideal interfacial behaviour [13]. The fit of all impedance dispersion
175 data are calculated with Boukamp's software until X^2 values around 10^{-5} are reached. An
176 example of the fitting of the impedance data presented in Fig. 2 is shown in Fig. 3 and
177 the resulting fitting values are collected in Table S2-S6, in the Supplementary
178 Information [8]. The two-arc model used by other authors does not work in our case,
179 where a three-arc model is needed to obtain a better fit and to account for the electronic
180 conductivity change predicted by DFT calculations [4]. Fig. S3 of the Supplementary
181 Information shows the difference of using a two-arc and a three-arc model; additionally
182 the obtained fitting results are collected in Table S7. As it can be seen in Fig. 3, the used
183 model slightly deviates from the experimental data at very low frequencies when Na^+
184 insertion has not started yet, i.e. in the 1.0-0.6 V window. This deviation can be mainly
185 attributed to an error when fitting the C_i , because in this potential range: (a) the
186 experimental C_i contribution to overall impedance is totally overlapped by the low-
187 frequency arc related to $R_{\text{elec}}//C_{\text{elec}}$; (b) the expected C_i values are very small and their
188 determination is only reliable when Na^+ insertion starts and C_i reaches significant values.
189

190

191 Fig. 3. The fitting of the Nyquist plot of $\text{Na}_{2+x}\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ electrode at the potential of a) 1.0 V, 0.88
 192 V, 0.70 V, 0.68 V, 0.65 V, 0.63 V, 0.60 V and b) 0.48 V, 0.45 V, 0.40 V, 0.35 V, 0.30 V, 0.18 V
 193 and 0.05 V vs. Na^+/Na . The inset shows the corresponding impedance spectra from 100
 194 kHz to 7 Hz.

195 The overall trend of the resistance values, calculated by fitting the EIS spectra, is
 196 reported in Fig. 4a and directly compared with the voltage during the intercalation and
 197 deintercalation sweeps. The most relevant trend observed is an abrupt decay of R_{elec} ,
 198 upon Na^+ insertion as already mentioned. In addition, such behaviour is reversible and
 199 the high R_{elec} values are recovered during Na^+ extraction. In the first insertion process,
 200 around 0.6 V vs. Na^+/Na , the only exception of a variation on R_{elec} can be observed, which
 201 is related with the irreversible reaction between $\text{Na}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ and Super C65 carbon [1]. As
 202 regards R_{CT} , the calculated values steadily increase during the first three cycles, which
 203 can be related with morphology changes of the $\text{Na}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ particles. The estimated values
 204 of “ a ” associated to R_{CT} confirm this hypothesis since a decrease is observed upon cycling
 205 (Fig. 4b), being “ a ” in the EIS fit, the exponential factor of CPEs that defines the surface
 206 homogeneity and roughness (“ a ” = 1 for surfaces completely homogeneous and
 207 smooth) [13].

208

209

210 Fig. 4. a) R_{sol} , R_{SEI} , R_{CT} and R_{elec} behaviour and values during the first three electrochemical
 211 cycles vs. voltage (Ewe vs. Na^+/Na). b) Values for the exponential a factor of the CPE
 212 associated with C_{DL} . Inset shows the equivalent circuit used to fit the impedance data.

213 Moreover, by comparing the behaviours of R_{elec} and R_{CT} it is possible to describe the
 214 intercalation kinetics of $\text{Na}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$. When the potential is above 0.13 V vs. Na^+/Na the R_{elec}
 215 is higher than R_{CT} , but when the potential is under 0.13 V the $R_{\text{elec}}:R_{\text{CT}}$ ratio is reversed.
 216 This confirms that, prior to large Na^+ insertion, the $\text{Na}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ behaves as an insulator and
 217 the intercalation kinetics are limited by the electronic conductivity but, when the
 218 amount of intercalated Na^+ increases, the $\text{Na}_{2+x}\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ behaves as a metallic conductor
 219 and the kinetics are limited by the interfacial charge-transfer step. As for the already
 220 investigated Li-ion battery materials [15], this transition in electron conduction
 221 properties is probably related to changes in the material lattice. This is in agreement
 222 with Barsoukov et al. [12,13] assignment where the low-frequency arc is attributed to
 223 changes in the crystal structure.

224 Finally, the R_{sol} is almost constant upon cycling. However, the SEI layer resistance (R_{SEI})
225 has a similar reversible behaviour as that shown by the R_{elec} . The RSEI is lower upon Na^+
226 insertion than after the extraction process; that can be explained by the fact that in the
227 first case the SEI layer is forming and when the voltage is decreasing the surface of the
228 SEI layer might be more homogeneously or smoothly distributed as suggests the “ α ”
229 value associated to C_{SEI} since the value is closer to the ideal (“ α ” = 1.0) (Fig.S4) whilst, in
230 the latter case, the SEI resistance increased due to the composition and properties of
231 the SEI layer is changing. As it has been recently shown by means of XPS and determining
232 the Auger parameter [6], upon Na^+ extraction a cracking of the SEI layer and/ or partial
233 dissolution of its components, such as NaCO_3R , occurs which will lead to a worsening of
234 the kinetic properties that is translated into a resistance increase. Moreover, it is
235 interesting to point out that at 1.0 V during the 1st Na^+ insertion, the electrode surface
236 already exhibits a SEI layer resistance which can be correlated with the spontaneous
237 formation of NaF and NaCl observed before any electrochemical cycling that is triggered
238 by the PVdF dehydrofluorination reaction along with the NaClO_4 decomposition [6].

239

240 4. Conclusions

241 The electrochemical impedance spectroscopy study here presented is the first
242 experimental demonstration of $\text{Na}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ ionic and electronic transport kinetics,
243 including determination of resistance, capacitance, “ α ” factor and CPE for the different
244 interfaces in the SEI layer. The R_{CT} gradual increases along the first three cycles along
245 with the decrease of its corresponding “ α ” factor has been correlated with morphology
246 changes of the $\text{Na}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ particles which would be consistent with the observed capacity
247 fading. These changes are deviations from the ideal interface, namely changes in the
248 active grain surface such as inhomogeneity, roughness and aggregations. For the first
249 time, a transition from electronic insulator to conductor in $\text{Na}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ electrodes for NIBs
250 is reported, such behaviour has never been observed in any other Na-based material.
251 This reversible transition is originated by Na^+ insertion/extraction into the $\text{Na}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$
252 structure, and more specifically, according to first-principles calculations reported
253 elsewhere, ascribed to the ionized electrons from the inserted Na that occupy the t_{2g}
254 orbitals of the Ti 3d in the $\text{Na}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ conduction band. Moreover, the instability of the SEI
255 layer has been also reported on the grounds of a resistance increase upon Na^+
256 extraction, contributing to the capacity fading widely reported for this material.
257 Therefore, new electrolytes that, combined with novel electrode formulations, form a
258 stable SEI layer are necessary to obtain good electrochemical performance.

259

260 Conflict of interest

261 We confirm there is no conflict of interest.

262

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